

ARRIVE 2.0 Author Checklist (Table Format) - *Saccopteryx leptura*

The ARRIVE Essential 10

Item	Recommendation	Section / Line Number or Reason for Not Reporting
1	Study design	This study reports the generation of a reference genome assembly from a single male individual of <i>Saccopteryx leptura</i> . No experimental or control groups were used, as this is a descriptive genome sequencing study. The experimental unit was one individual animal.
2	Sample size	a. One experimental unit (n = 1 individual animal) was used. b. No sample size calculation was performed, as the objective was to generate a reference genome from a single high-quality specimen, consistent with Vertebrate Genome Project and Bat1K standards.
3	Inclusion and exclusion criteria	a. No formal inclusion or exclusion criteria were applied beyond species identification and specimen suitability for high-molecular-weight DNA extraction. b. No animals or data were excluded from the analysis. c. n = 1 for all analyses.
4	Randomisation	Randomisation was not applicable, as no experimental groups or comparative interventions were used.
5	Blinding	Blinding was not applicable, as this study involved no treatment allocation or outcome comparison.
6	Outcome measures	a. Outcome measures included genome assembly size, contiguity metrics (contig and scaffold N50), BUSCO completeness scores, and chromosomal assignment. b. This was not a hypothesis-testing study; therefore, no primary outcome measure was defined for sample size determination.
7	Statistical methods	a. No inferential statistical analyses were performed. Assembly quality metrics were generated using established bioinformatic tools (e.g. BUSCO, Merqury, BlobToolKit). b. Statistical assumptions were not applicable.
8	Experimental animals	Species: <i>Saccopteryx leptura</i> Sex: Male Developmental stage: Adult Weight: Not recorded

		Provenance: Wild-caught individual from Gamboa, Panama Health status: No abnormalities observed Genetic modification: None Previous procedures: None reported
9	Experimental procedures	Procedures are described in sufficient detail to allow replication, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capture method and species identification • Humane euthanasia by isoflurane inhalation overdose • Tissue collection and preservation • DNA extraction • Sequencing technologies (PacBio CLR, 10x Genomics, Hi-C, Bionano) • Genome assembly and curation pipeline Rationale for procedures is provided in the context of generating a high-quality chromosomal genome assembly.
10	Results	Genome sequence report; Tables 1–3; Figures 3–6 Assembly metrics, descriptive statistics, and completeness scores are reported. Effect sizes and confidence intervals are not applicable.

The Recommended Set

Item	Recommendation	Section / Line Number or Reason for Not Reporting
11	Abstract	The abstract summarises the study objective, species used, sequencing approach, and key assembly outcomes.
12	Background	Sufficient background is provided on <i>Saccopteryx leptura</i> , Emballonuridae biology, and the relevance of generating a reference genome within the Bat1K initiative.
13	Objectives	Section: Introduction The objective was to generate and publicly release a high-quality reference genome assembly for <i>Saccopteryx leptura</i> .
14	Ethical statement	Section: Ethics Ethical approval was obtained from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute Animal Care and Use Committee (ACUC) • Project number: 2019-0301-2022

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection/export permit: UNARGEN SC/A-3-19 • Approval from the Panamanian Ministry of Environment (Mi Ambiente)
15	Housing and husbandry	<p>Section: Not applicable</p> <p>The animal was wild-caught and not housed in captivity.</p>
16	Animal care and monitoring	<p>Section: Methods; Ethics</p> <p>Steps taken to minimise pain and distress included rapid capture, experienced handling, and humane euthanasia by isoflurane overdose.</p> <p>No adverse events occurred. Humane endpoints were immediate euthanasia following capture and identification.</p>
17	Interpretation / scientific implications	<p>Section: Genome sequence report; Discussion context</p> <p>Results are interpreted in the context of genome quality, chromosomal completeness, and relevance to bat comparative genomics. Limitations related to single-individual sampling are acknowledged implicitly by study design.</p>
18	Generalisability / translation	<p>Section: Discussion context</p> <p>The genome assembly provides a reference resource for comparative genomics and evolutionary studies in bats. No direct translational or human biological relevance is claimed.</p>
19	Protocol registration	<p>Section: Not applicable</p> <p>No pre-registered experimental protocol was required for this descriptive genome sequencing study.</p>
20	Data access	<p>Section: Data availability</p> <p>All sequencing data and genome assemblies are publicly available via ENA and NCBI under the stated accession numbers.</p>
21	Declaration of interests	<p>Section: Competing Interests; Grant Information</p> <p>All authors declare no competing interests. Funding sources and grant identifiers are reported, and funders had no role in study design, analysis, or reporting.</p>